

* SYNTHESIS OF CAMOQUIN ANALOGUES

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Synthesis of 2-methylcamoquin and the corresponding piperidinomethyl analogue has been described.

Metabolic studies on quinine (Mead and Koepfli, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, 154, 104) have demonstrated the formation of 2-hydroxyquinoline derivative in presence of liver. It was speculated that if the 2-position of the quinoline ring be blocked by a suitable grouping, there might be an enhancement of activity. This consideration was supported by the observation that α -(2-piperidyl)-2-phenyl-4-quinoline-methanol was much more effective against avian malaria than the corresponding compound without the 2-phenyl group (Raport *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2697). It was accordingly considered worthwhile to synthesise a 2-methyl analogue of 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-diethylaminomethyl)-anilinoquinoline (Camoquin), in view of the pronounced antimalarial activity of the latter. The corresponding piperidinomethyl analogue was also synthesised. 7-Chloro 2-methyl-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-diethylaminomethyl)-anilinoquinoline was synthesised by first condensing *p*-aminophenol with 4:7-dichloroquinaldine and the resulting condensate, 7-chloro-2-methyl-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinoline was then subjected to the usual Mannich reaction with diethylamine and paraformaldehyde to furnish the desired compound. There are two vulnerable positions where the diethylaminomethyl group can enter, either at the position adjacent to the hydroxy group of the aniline or at the methyl group lying at the 2-position of the quinoline nucleus. The identity of the resulting Mannich base has been established by its unambiguous synthesis from 4:7-dichloroquinaldine and 4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethylaniline, which indicates that the hydroxy group preferentially influences the reaction. The compounds were prepared according to the general method described by Burckhalter *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1363; 1950 72, 1024).

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilino-2-methylquinoline.—To a solution of *p*-aminophenol hydrochloride (4.85 g.) in water (50 c.c.) 4:7-dichloro-2-methylquinoline (7 g.) was added. The mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 4 hours and then allowed to stand for two days. The crystalline material was collected and stirred with excess of ammonia. The solid product was filtered off, washed thoroughly with water, dried in air and was then recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 274-75°. (Found: N, 9.56. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 9.81%).

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7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-diethylaminomethyl)-anilino-2-methylquinoline:—(a). 2-Diethylaminomethyl-4-acetamidophenol (6.4 g.) was heated under reflux with HCl (conc., 12.8 c.c.) for 1 hour. To the cooled solution, adjusted to p_H 4 by addition of 50% NaOH solution (aq.), 4:7-dichloroquinaldine (5.3 g.) was then added and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 3 hours. The oily liquid separating at the bottom solidified *en masse* in course of heating. The reaction mixture was then dissolved in 150 c.c. of hot water (charcoal), filtered, cooled and basified with a slight excess of ammonia. This was collected, washed thoroughly and was twice recrystallised from aqueous ethyl alcohol to afford a colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 183-84°. (Found: N, 11.06. $C_{21}H_{24}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 11.36%).

(b). A mixture of 7-chloro-2-methyl-4-(4'-hydroxy)-anilinoquinoline (8.7 g.), paraformaldehyde (1.0 g.), diethylamine (15 c.c.) and rectified spirit (30 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 8 hours on a water-bath. After the period the excess of diethylamine and alcohol were evaporated off. The residue was dissolved in 3% HCl (200 c.c.), charcoaled and filtered. After cooling, the solution was basified with a slight excess of ammonia, filtered, washed thoroughly and sucked as dry as possible. The wet cake was dissolved in a minimum amount of rectified spirit (charcoal) and filtered. On cooling a crystalline solid separated. This was dried and twice recrystallised from aqueous ethyl alcohol, m.p. 183-84°. Mixed m.p. with the sample prepared by the method described above recorded no depression.

7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy-3'-N-piperidylmethyl)-anilino-2-methylquinoline:—2-N-Piperidylmethyl-*p*-acetamidophenol (6.2 g.) was heated under reflux with 20% aqueous HCl (14 c.c.) for 1 hour. To the cold mixture, adjusted to p_H 4 with 20% aqueous NaOH solution (aq.), 4:7-dichloroquinaldine (5.3 g.) was added and heated on a steam bath for 4 hours. The solution was cooled, diluted with double its volume of water and basified with a slight excess of dilute ammonia. The solid was collected, washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 120-21° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.89. $C_{22}H_{24}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 11.00%).